

Information Security of Ukraine at the Present Stage of State Development

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Abstract: The article explores problems related to the directions of public policy in the field development of information security. Based on analysis of scientific literature in the work stated that information security is state of protection of the individual, society, against harmful or unlawful information from information that has a negative impact on the consciousness of the individual, impedes sustainable development of the individual, society and state. Information security is a state of security of information infrastructure, including computers and information and telecommunications infrastructure and the information they have, which also ensures the sustainable development of the individual, society and the state. Legal database does not cover all the basic elements needed to effectively counteract the information threats to some extent obsolete because the latest political trends are shaping political realities that bring information security issues to the fore.

Problem setting

The beginning of the 21st century is characterized new political and economic situation, in Ukraine, which actively and consistently upholds its national interests in the global world. These interests are in the range and Ukraine's participation in information processes, which is most closely connected with the security of the state, society, economic entities, each individuals in the information field.

The current state of social development characterized as a stage of formation of the information society. Implementation the latest information technology is significant accelerates the process of receiving, processing, analysis of information. Wide and prompt access to information increases efficiency its use, which becomes an integral part of managing all institutions and processes.

Modern Ukraine is fully involved in the processes of informatization of society and society formation of a single world information market. The information factor plays significant role in the state-making process, in representation and upholding the interests of the state. A special place in this spectrum of public relations are occupied by problems of legal support of information security.

Recent research and publications analysis

The conducted doctrinal analysis of the problems of information security showed that, despite the great interest in this issue, its study is mainly of technical and applied nature and focused on solving specific scientific and technical problems. The research of theoretical

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and practical aspects of information security, addressed to the role of information processes, is devoted to the work of domestic scientists O. Bodruk, A. Kachinsky, V. Krysachenko, S. PyrozHKov, T. Starodub, O. Shevchenko, while information security as one of the components of national safety was not considered by scientists, which caused the scientific interest of the author. The research of theoretical and practical aspects of information security, addressed to the role of information processes, is devoted to the work of domestic scientists O. Bodruk, O. Vlasyuk, V. Gorbulin, A. Kachinsky, V. Krysachenko, O. Manachinsky, B. Parakhonsky, S. PyrozHKov, T. Starodub, O. Shevchenko and others.

Conceptual problems of information security are considered in the works of domestic and foreign scientists: R. Aron, K. Gadzhiev, K. Clausewitz, B. Liddell-Harte, N. Machiavelli, H. Moltke, K. Popper, P. Proudhon, E. Rybkin, S. Tyushkevich, M. Tsyurupa, A. Schweitzer, and others. Problems of information-psychological confrontation and information wars, as well as issues of interaction of state and state administration are devoted to the works of L. Artyushin, M. Varia, V. Korendovich, V. Krysk, V. Lisichkin, O. Litvinenko, S. Mosov, V. Tolubka and others.

Objectives setting

The purpose of this article is to study the peculiarities of information security of Ukraine, taking into account the current stage of historical development of the state-constitutional system.

Paper main body

With Ukraine becoming independent and proclaiming and implementing a course on democratic, humanistic ideas and values, the problems of building and implementing information security are becoming more acute and relevant. At the same time, the modern world is filled with multifaceted aspects and features that characterize information security in a dynamic dimension that goes far beyond the doctrinal conception of that definition, particularly in the context of the emergence of a global information society. The beginning of the third millennium was marked by the birth of a new type of information society, in which information is the main strategic resource. The impact of information processes on all spheres of public and social life actualizes the most important issues of social life, including issues of information interactions, including the fight for information space and counteracting various kinds of information threats. In this regard, one can not change the situation regarding the study of the value orientation of the individual, his information justification and information security. In modern literature, information security is understood to mean its protection against accidental or deliberate interference with its functioning, from attempts to steal, modify, and destroy its components. The scientific doctrine of information security of Ukraine provides a comprehensive definition of information security. It should be understood as a state of protection of national interests in the information environment, which determines the set of balanced interests of the individual, society and state.

According to the scientist MV Arsenyev, information security is the removal of information uncertainty of real or potential threats due to the control over the world information space and the availability of opportunities and means to reflect these threats [1].

In the article "Information Security of Ukraine in Modern Cyberspace" by K.L Burich, I.N Efimenko, B.D Kogan to the computer The most common crimes include theft of money,

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things, machine information, machine time, unauthorized use of the system, sabotage and blackmail, espionage, vandalism. They consider it the most common species cybercrime is the theft of money in electronic banking settlement systems. According to them, it accounts for about 45% of all crimes, computer-related.

The aforementioned scholars note that today, Ukraine is in a state of information warfare with countries trying to impose their values on our country, to destroy the traditional moral and ethical ones principles of Ukrainian society, development information technology has led to that information expansion is taking place systematically, and crimes against information security is becoming more sophisticated and dangerous. Recently, he has been getting information new features that determine its socio-economic value and legal content. IN first of all, information is nowadays perceived as an important economic resource. In the article "Legal regulation of information security in the field of business activity »V. Nikolaev, G. Ostapovich, I. Kostitskaya notes that the use of information resources is an effective organization of information processes can significantly increase your profitability many productive activities, contribute to solving political, military-political, socio-economic, cultural, educational and social problems. The information also becomes economical a product that stimulates the growth of a new segment of the national economy, information services, worldwide. Like any goods, information has the owner who has the right to dispose of information on your own discretion, and its unauthorized use entails material, reputational losses to its rightful owner, unauthorized actions with information become the basis for harm to the state, citizens, business entities [2].

Information security is a component of overall security and is rapidly evolving as worldwide, as well as in Ukraine, global informatization covers all spheres of the state - economic, military, political, industrial, etc. Information security, like any other object, has threats that affect both the physical integrity and its derivatives. As you know, information security, protection which, according to Art. 117 of the Constitution of Ukraine, along with sovereignty, territorial integrity and economic security, is the most important function of the state, achieved through development and implementation modern secure information technologies, construction of functionally complete national infrastructure, formation and the development of information relations, etc. [3].

According to the Law "On Fundamentals of National Security of Ukraine" one of the main threats to the national interests and national security of Ukraine in information sphere is an attempt to manipulate the public consciousness, in particular by disseminating inaccurate, incomplete or biased information. Along with this Art. 3 of the Law of Ukraine "On information "indicates that the main directions of state information policy are: ensuring everyone's access to information; ensuring equal opportunities for create, collect, receive, store, use, distribute, protect, protection of information; creating the conditions for formation of an information society in Ukraine; ensuring the openness and transparency of the activities of the authorities; creation of information systems and networks of information, development of electronic management; continuous updating, enrichment and storage of national information resources; providing information security of Ukraine; promoting international cooperation in the information sphere and Ukraine's accession to the world information space [4]. In turn, the Law of Ukraine "On basics of national security »three national and, accordingly, information security objects, including:

- man and citizen - their constitutional rights and freedoms;
- society - its spiritual, moral, cultural, historical. Intellectual and material values, information and environment and natural resource;
- the state is its constitutional system, sovereignty, territorial integrity and inviolability [5].

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To achieve this goal on information security system is assigned certain tasks, the main thing among which is the creation of conditions for the organization effective management of information threats elimination system.

Legal and regulatory regulation of the information security system Ukraine is represented by: the Constitution of Ukraine, the Law of Ukraine "On the basics of national security of Ukraine", the Law of Ukraine "On Information", Law of Ukraine "On Concept of the National Program of Informatization », other normative legal acts.

Along with the legal direction, information security policy is implemented as a system of public institutions. authorities and civic institutions the societies to which it relates resolving the issues of creating safe conditions for functioning and development of the information sphere.

Composition of information security mechanism determined by the rules of Art. 4 of the Law of Ukraine "On the Basics of National Security of Ukraine": President of Ukraine, Verkhovna Rada Of Ukraine, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, the Council national security and defense of Ukraine, ministries and other central executive bodies, National Bank of Ukraine, courts of general jurisdiction, prosecutor's office Ukraine, local state administrations and local self-government bodies: Armed Forces of Ukraine, Security Service of Ukraine, State Border Guard Service of Ukraine and other military formations formed in accordance with the laws of Ukraine. Important information security tasks are undoubtedly performed by the Security Service Ukraine, which according to the norms of Art. 1 of the Law "On the Security Service of Ukraine" is defined as "a state law enforcement agency special purpose that provides state security of Ukraine "[6].

Conclusions of the research

The legal framework does not cover everything the essentials needed to be effective counteracting certain information threats as old as the latest political ones trends shape political reality.

This requires improvement of the system regulation of state policy in the field of information security development in the conditions of information war. It is about the need to establish a clear hierarchical unity of legal acts in the field of information the security of the country and each individual region; streamlining information sharing and information and analytical support work of state authorities, other public institutions with state bodies authorities and among themselves, ensuring the unconditional observance of information security requirements by officials, citizens; development of regulatory framework in the industry the use of Internet networks and the protection of state information resources; delimiting access order other states or foreigners to the information resources of Ukraine and the procedure for their use in accordance with agreements with others states.

It also requires the application of criminal law aimed at protection of the state and citizens in the sphere of information activity from computer manifestations, information crime and cyberterrorism. Institutionally, it seems appropriate to develop a strategic one in Ukraine a document that should provide clear answers to questions about her ideas about the "new digital order" and describe the steps the government is ready to take to create / counteract it. In this case, each institute of state management, which is in one way or another involved in the information security system security, should form an appropriate unit to take care of the issue, and coordinate the activities of these structures National Security and Defense Council. Except addition, methods of providing information Ukraine's security includes: developing programs for providing information security for Ukraine and determining their order financing; improving the financing system for work related to implementation legal

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and organizational-technical methods of information protection, system creation insurance of information risks of individuals and legal entities. To protect the Ukrainian space from external advocacy and coordination the activity of the private media to bring information to citizens in the occupied territories on December 2, 2014, the Ministry of Information Policy of Ukraine was established. At the same time, there is an existing mechanism for implementing state development policy information security cannot be considered perfect. Evidence of this was Russia's actual capture of information the area of Crimea, East and South of Ukraine, that created the preconditions for the Russian occupation of the ARC and the organization of armed conflict in the Donetsk and Lugansk regions. Now Russia's purposeful activities make it possible provoke tensions in other regions, maintain anti-Ukrainian sentiment among its own population, to discredit Ukraine and justify its policy in EU Member States. Scientists say that the element of response to this problem is the creation of a nationwide information system (including cybernetic) security of Ukraine offensive focus on both the protection of sovereignty and the promotion of Ukrainian national interests. This involves:

- development and improvement of the legal and regulatory framework in the field of information security, which is now fragmented and incomplete to meet urgent needs;
- creation (definition) of the governing and the coordinating body of the information security system of Ukraine in the structure of state bodies of executive power;
- definition (refinement) of the list entities responsible for information security;
- conducting research and determination needs for technical, financial and personnel support of the system functioning;
- intensification of activities at the Ministry of Defense and the General Staff of the Armed Forces Ukraine to create its own information security system as a component of national information security systems [7].

Therefore, in protecting its information interests, Ukraine must take care of its information security, and so does strengthening Ukrainian statehood. Balanced state information security policy Ukraine is formed as an integral part of it socio-economic policies based on prioritizing national interests and threats to national security. From a legal point of view, it is based on principles the rule of law and is implemented through the development and implementation of relevant national doctrines, strategies, concepts and programs in accordance with applicable law. The system of regulatory acts that regulate relations in the information sphere, often limited only by declarations standards, it needs significant improvement and adaptation to modern realities. There was a need to build a conceptually new system of public administration and information system as its component [8].

Thus, the improvement of the legal support of the state information development policy security in an information war should regarded as a leading direction of the state policies aimed at protecting interests citizens of Ukraine, society and the state.

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